

Value of playgrounds relative to green spaces: Matching evidence from property prices in Australia

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Key findings

We use urban Australian property sales data and match properties near small playgrounds to similar properties near two empty, open green spaces which are candidates for playground construction to show:

- The presence of a playground within 300 metres adds about AU\$20,000 (4.6 per cent) to the average property price.
- The price effect of a playground is larger for houses than for apartments and falls with distance from the playground.
- The results suggest that these estimates of the value that property purchasers place on playgrounds should be taken into account by municipalities when considering investment.

What we knew

- Open/green space, air quality, lakes, wetlands, undisturbed areas, nationally significant landscapes, cultural sites and other amenities have significant and positive effects on prices and rents of urban properties in the proximity (Waltert and Schlöpfer; 2010).
- Investment in urban green areas increases property price (Morancho; 2003; Panduro and Veie; 2013).
- The impact of amenities on property prices are heterogeneous (Anderson and West; 2006; Livy and Klaiber; 2016).

What we do

- We use individual transaction data for properties sold between January 2005 and December 2014, collected by Australian Property Monitors (APM).
- We construct a matched sample of ‘treatment properties’ near playgrounds that we compare to a set of ‘control properties’ that are near two empty green spaces that have been identified as possible locations for playground infrastructure investment.
- We use the hedonic model to control for observable differences in properties and then compare the unexplained component of average house prices across treatment and control groups to obtain an estimate of the average impact of a playground relative to an empty green space.

What we know now

- Effects of playgrounds on property price vary from about AU\$15,000 to about AU\$35,000 depending upon the distance from the playground and the type of property considered.
- These effects range from 3.4 per cent to 7.9 per cent of median property price.
- The impact falls as we move further away from the playground.

- The impact is larger if we consider only houses instead of all properties.

What this means for policy

- The capitalized value of playgrounds in property prices need to be considered as an important input into any cost-benefit analysis of investing in playground infrastructure.
- Homeowners should not be worried (and object) to the construction of new playgrounds as they do not lower housing prices; rather they add to home value.
- Landholders may approach local governments or even band together themselves to make investments in the construction of new playgrounds.

Where to now?

- It is important to examine the social benefits of playgrounds as property prices capture the private valuation of families of proximity to an amenity and may not capture all of types of benefits they provide.
- More studies that exploit price changes before and after playground construction would help to show how the impact changes with distances from the amenity.

More information

- Get the full working paper at: https://crawford.anu.edu.au/files/uploads/crawford01_cap_anu_edu_au/2018-04/playgrounds_wp_march2018.pdf or the published version at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169204618301294>
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au.

References

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